

Impact of Hyperprior Choice for Bayesian Dynamic Borrowing via a Normalized Power Prior

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Abstract

In clinical trial design, growing attention is being given to the use of Bayesian methods to reduce sample size requirements in rare disease trials by borrowing information from external data sources. One proposed borrowing method is the ‘power prior’, in which an informative prior is formed based on the parameter likelihood for the external data raised to the power of a discount parameter $\alpha_0 \in [0, 1]$. The normalized power prior (NPP) builds upon this approach by placing a hyperprior on the discount parameter to allow for dynamic borrowing based on the compatibility of the data sources. The choice of NPP discount parameter hyperprior has the potential to materially impact the amount of information borrowed. The objective of this study is to characterize the influence of different choices of hyperprior for the NPP discounting parameter on the amount of information borrowing from external data sources. We examine the impacts of the hyperprior choice under various sample size and sample response rate scenarios in a setting with borrowing across two single-arm trials with binary response endpoints.

Keywords: Power priors, Bayesian borrowing, dynamic borrowing, normalized power prior, clinical trials, complex innovative trial designs

1 Introduction

Evaluating efficacy and safety for novel therapies in rare indications can be challenging due to the difficulty of recruiting enough patients to conduct a well-powered clinical trial. These challenges have spurred interest in complex and innovative trial designs which allow for borrowing of information from external data sources to supplement limited trial sample sizes[1] or reduce control group allocation in a hybrid-controlled trial[2]—often through the use of Bayesian methods.

The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has provided guidance on considerations for the appropriate use of Bayesian methods to borrow information from external data sources[3, 4, 5]. This includes the importance of selecting a suitable external data source and evaluating the type-I and type-II error operating characteristics under the proposed borrowing approach.

Power prior methods (including the normalized power prior) have been proposed as a means of borrowing information from external data sources (e.g. historical trial control

arms) to supplement trial data while allowing for down-weighting of the external data’s influence[6, 7].

Normalized power priors (NPP) allow for dynamic borrowing in which the amount of borrowing from the external data is driven by the degree of similarity in outcomes between the current trial and external data source—a desirable property that can reduce type-I error by borrowing less when the current and external data sources are inconsistent[1]. This is achieved by treating the power prior weight or “discount parameter” as a parameter to be learned from the data. However, when borrowing from a single external data source, the amount of borrowing has the potential to be sensitive to the choice of hyperprior for the discount parameter—i.e. the hyperprior has the potential to materially impact the posterior distribution for the NPP discount parameter.

The goal of this paper is to characterize how the choice of NPP discount parameter hyperprior impacts the ability of the method to facilitate greater information borrowing when outcomes are compatible between current and external/historical data sources, and temper borrowing when outcomes differ substantially between data sources.

2 Methods

2.1 Overview of Power Priors

2.1.1 Static Power Prior Formulation for Bayesian Borrowing

When performing inference on a parameter θ using data from a current data source, D , we may want to borrow information from an appropriate and available historical/external data source D_0 .

Ignoring the external data, the posterior for θ given our current data D would be

$$\pi(\theta|D) \propto L(\theta|D)\pi_0(\theta) \quad ,$$

where $L(\theta|D)$ is the likelihood for the current data D , and $\pi_0(\theta)$ is our prior for θ before observing any data.

If we now consider the external data source, D_0 , we can improve upon this approach using an informative prior based on D_0 . The power prior[6, 7] provides one such method for borrowing information from D_0 to improve the precision of the posterior for θ . The power prior for θ is based on the likelihood for the external data, $L(\theta|D_0)$, but allows for down-weighting of the contribution of D_0 by means of a discount parameter, $\alpha_0 \in [0, 1]$. It takes the following form:

$$\pi(\theta|D_0, \alpha_0) \propto L(\theta|D_0)^{\alpha_0}\pi_0(\theta) \quad .$$

We can now reformulate the posterior for θ using this informative power prior:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(\theta|D, D_0, \alpha_0) &\propto L(\theta|D)\pi(\theta|D_0, \alpha_0) \\ &\propto L(\theta|D)L(\theta|D_0)^{\alpha_0}\pi_0(\theta) \quad , \end{aligned}$$

which shows how the posterior depends on both the current data and the discounted external data. A key property of this power prior approach is that if $\alpha_0 = 0$ no information is incorporated from D_0 and, if $\alpha_0 = 1$, then the data D_0 is given full weight and is analogous to pooling the data for D and D_0 .

2.1.2 Dynamic Bayesian Borrowing via a Normalized Power Prior (NPP)

The above static power prior model with fixed α_0 can be extended to a dynamic borrowing setting by making the α_0 discount parameter a random variable rather than fixed [6, 7]. This allows for the weight on the external data to be dynamically updated based on the degree of inconsistency between data sources. In this case our power prior becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}\pi(\theta, \alpha_0 | D_0) &= \pi(\theta | \alpha_0, D_0) \pi(\alpha_0 | D_0) \\ &= [c(\alpha_0) L(\theta | D_0)^{\alpha_0} \pi_0(\theta)] [\pi_0(\alpha_0)] \\ &= \left[\frac{L(\theta | D_0)^{\alpha_0} \pi_0(\theta)}{\int_{\Theta} L(\theta | D_0)^{\alpha_0} \pi_0(\theta) d\theta} \right] [\pi_0(\alpha_0)] \quad .\end{aligned}$$

We substitute $\pi(\alpha_0 | D_0) = \pi_0(\alpha_0)$ above since our hyperprior does not depend on the external data D_0 . As Neuenschwander et al. [8] note, the normalizing constant $c(\alpha_0) = 1 / \int_{\Theta} L(\theta | D_0)^{\alpha_0} \pi_0(\theta) d\theta$ cannot be ignored since it depends on α_0 . This formulation of the NPP was implemented by Duan [9].

2.2 Model Specification

We focus on a case of borrowing into a current single-arm trial with a binary response endpoint from a lone historical single-arm trial. This example can easily be extended to a hybrid-controlled setting (e.g. if the current single-arm trial were replaced with a 2-arm RCT with a common control arm treatment). Adjustments for differences in baseline covariates between data sources can also be incorporated as a further extension [6, 7]. The current and historical data for this case are, respectively, $D = (n, y)$ and $D_0 = (n_0, y_0)$, and the response rate parameter of interest is θ .

We use the following priors for θ and α_0 :

$$\begin{aligned}\theta &\sim \text{Beta}(a, b) \\ \alpha_0 &\sim \text{Beta}(c, d) \quad .\end{aligned}$$

We start by deriving $\pi(\theta | \alpha_0, D_0)$:

$$\begin{aligned}\pi(\theta | \alpha_0, D_0) &= \frac{L(\theta | D_0)^{\alpha_0} \pi_0(\theta)}{\int_{\Theta} L(\theta | D_0)^{\alpha_0} \pi_0(\theta) d\theta} \\ &= c(\alpha_0) L(\theta | D_0)^{\alpha_0} \pi_0(\theta) \\ &= c(\alpha_0) \cdot [k_1 \theta^{y_0} (1 - \theta)^{n_0 - y_0}]^{\alpha_0} k_2 \cdot \theta^{a-1} (1 - \theta)^{b-1} \\ &\propto \theta^{\alpha_0 y_0 + a - 1} (1 - \theta)^{\alpha_0 (n_0 - y_0) + b - 1} \quad ,\end{aligned}$$

where $c(\alpha_0)$, k_1 and k_2 are constants. From here we can see that:

$$\theta | \alpha_0, D_0 \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_0 y_0 + a, \alpha_0 (n_0 - y_0) + b) \quad .$$

We can then combine $\pi(\theta|\alpha_0, D_0)$ and $\pi(\alpha_0|D_0) = \pi_0(\alpha_0)$ to compute the power prior:

$$\begin{aligned}\pi(\theta, \alpha_0|D_0) &= \pi(\theta|\alpha_0, D_0)\pi(\alpha_0|D_0) \\ &= \pi(\theta|\alpha_0, D_0)\pi_0(\alpha_0) \\ &= \frac{1}{B(\alpha_0 y_0 + a, \alpha_0(n_0 - y_0) + b)} \theta^{\alpha_0 y_0 + a - 1} (1 - \theta)^{\alpha_0(n_0 - y_0) + b - 1} \\ &\quad \times \frac{1}{B(c, d)} \alpha_0^{c-1} (1 - \alpha_0)^{d-1} .\end{aligned}$$

Lastly, we formulate our unnormalized posterior as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\pi(\theta, \alpha_0|D, D_0) &\propto L(\theta|D)\pi(\theta, \alpha_0|D_0) \\ &\propto \theta^y (1 - \theta)^{n-y} \\ &\quad \times \frac{1}{B(\alpha_0 y_0 + a, \alpha_0(n_0 - y_0) + b)} \theta^{\alpha_0 y_0 + a - 1} (1 - \theta)^{\alpha_0(n_0 - y_0) + b - 1} \\ &\quad \times \frac{1}{B(c, d)} \alpha_0^{c-1} (1 - \alpha_0)^{d-1} ,\end{aligned}$$

which can then be used to estimate the final posterior via Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods.

2.3 Simulation

Under a variety of α_0 discount parameter hyperprior, sample size (n, n_0) and sample response rate (p, p_0) scenarios, we compute the joint posterior $\pi(\theta, \alpha_0|D, D_0)$ via MCMC. We focus our attention on how the power prior discount parameter is updated from the hyperprior to the marginal posterior under the various sample size and sample response rate scenarios. We also report posterior summary statistics for the θ response rate parameter to gauge the influence of the external data on response rate estimates when there are discrepancies between the observed response in the current and external/historical datasets. We consider several choices of Beta hyperpriors: a U-shaped Beta(0.5, 0.5) distribution, a uniform Beta(1, 1), and a right-skewed Beta(2, 1). We opt to set $a = 1$ and $b = 1$ so that θ has a Uniform(0, 1) prior.

MCMC was implemented using the Stan No U-Turn Sampler (NUTS) Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) variant[10]. We used 4 chains, 100,000 iterations per chain and a burn-in length of 10,000. No thinning was applied. Analyses were conducted in the R programming language[11] with Stan invoked via the *rstan* package[12]. MCMC convergence was assessed using trace plots and \hat{R} statistics[13]. Complete simulation code is provided in appendix A.2.

3 Results

Evaluation of trace plots and \hat{R} statistics indicate that MCMC convergence was achieved (see appendix A.1 for additional details, including trace plots). Effective sample sizes for the NPP discount parameter (α_0) and response rate parameter (θ) exceeded 99,000 for all scenarios.

Table 1 presents the posterior means and 95% credible intervals (CrI) for the response rate (θ) and discount parameter (α_0) under each simulation scenario. For the discount pa-

parameter we focus our attention on the mean values to capture the amount of posterior mass placed on low vs. high borrowing weights due to the highly skewed and/or multimodal nature of the hyperprior and posterior distributions for this parameter.

Table 1: Results under Various Scenarios (Posterior Means and 95% Credible Intervals)

Hyperprior	p	p_0	$n : n_0$	Response Rate (θ)	Discount Param. (α_0)
Beta(0.5, 0.5)	0.4	0.2	100 : 100	0.377 [0.279, 0.479]	0.175 [0.000, 0.878]
Beta(0.5, 0.5)	0.4	0.2	100 : 200	0.378 [0.275, 0.480]	0.090 [0.000, 0.525]
Beta(0.5, 0.5)	0.4	0.3	100 : 100	0.371 [0.294, 0.464]	0.511 [0.006, 0.998]
Beta(0.5, 0.5)	0.4	0.3	100 : 200	0.361 [0.289, 0.457]	0.463 [0.005, 0.998]
Beta(0.5, 0.5)	0.4	0.4	100 : 100	0.401 [0.326, 0.479]	0.622 [0.019, 0.999]
Beta(0.5, 0.5)	0.4	0.4	100 : 200	0.401 [0.334, 0.470]	0.611 [0.022, 0.999]
Beta(1, 1)	0.4	0.2	100 : 100	0.368 [0.275, 0.468]	0.240 [0.010, 0.831]
Beta(1, 1)	0.4	0.2	100 : 200	0.364 [0.265, 0.467]	0.147 [0.005, 0.646]
Beta(1, 1)	0.4	0.3	100 : 100	0.371 [0.294, 0.459]	0.493 [0.038, 0.972]
Beta(1, 1)	0.4	0.3	100 : 200	0.359 [0.288, 0.447]	0.461 [0.031, 0.967]
Beta(1, 1)	0.4	0.4	100 : 100	0.401 [0.325, 0.480]	0.572 [0.066, 0.980]
Beta(1, 1)	0.4	0.4	100 : 200	0.401 [0.334, 0.471]	0.562 [0.063, 0.980]
Beta(2, 1)	0.4	0.2	100 : 100	0.346 [0.262, 0.445]	0.432 [0.060, 0.949]
Beta(2, 1)	0.4	0.2	100 : 200	0.333 [0.245, 0.439]	0.328 [0.034, 0.918]
Beta(2, 1)	0.4	0.3	100 : 100	0.364 [0.291, 0.444]	0.651 [0.158, 0.986]
Beta(2, 1)	0.4	0.3	100 : 200	0.348 [0.286, 0.422]	0.634 [0.139, 0.985]
Beta(2, 1)	0.4	0.4	100 : 100	0.401 [0.328, 0.476]	0.698 [0.209, 0.989]
Beta(2, 1)	0.4	0.4	100 : 200	0.401 [0.338, 0.465]	0.692 [0.202, 0.989]

Figure 1 shows how the Beta(0.5, 0.5) discount parameter hyperprior (in grey) is updated under each of the scenarios once the data is observed. This U-shaped hyperprior would be expected to favour either a high- or low-degree of borrowing from the external data and discourage partial borrowing. We see that when response rates differ substantially (0.4 vs 0.2) the posterior for the discount parameter has most of its mass near zero (i.e. less weight is placed on the external data and borrowing is tempered). This is particularly notable for the case where the sample size of the external data increases from 100 to 200, with the posterior mean value of discount parameter falling from 0.175 to 0.090. This makes intuitive sense since the larger sample size provides greater evidence of material differences in response rates between the two data sources.

While these results suggest that the NPP allows for substantial down-weighting of the external data when outcomes differ materially, we do not see a similar degree of up-weighting applied to the external data when response outcomes are identical (0.4 vs. 0.4). The posterior distribution for the discount parameter does tend to favour more borrowing than the hyperprior, but posterior means for the discount parameter don't increase substantially from 0.5 for the hyperprior to 0.622 and 0.611 where the external data sample size is 100 and 200, respectively.

Figure 2 plots the discount parameter posteriors under each scenario with a uniform Beta(1, 1) hyperprior. We again see that for large discrepancies in response rates (0.4 vs. 0.2) the posteriors are updated to favour lower discount parameter values with posterior means of 0.240 and 0.147 for the external data sample sizes of 100 and 200, respectively.

Figure 1: Discount Parameter Posteriors vs. Beta(0.5, 0.5) Hyperprior (grey)

However, when the response rates differ moderately (0.4 vs. 0.3) or are identical (0.4 vs. 0.4), the posteriors don't differ very substantially from the uniform hyperprior. Even where the response rates are identical between datasets, the posterior means remain close to the prior mean of 0.5 at values of 0.572 and 0.562 for external data samples sizes of 100 and 200, respectively.

Figure 3 plots the discount parameter posteriors under the Beta(2, 1) hyperprior for each scenario. Even though this hyperprior choice puts more weight on larger discount parameter values with a mean weight of 0.666, where there is a large discrepancy in response rates between datasets (0.4 vs. 0.2) the posterior still tends towards putting more weight on lower values with posterior means of 0.432 and 0.328 for external sample sizes of 100 and 200, respectively. As with the previous case, the posteriors for the 0.4 vs. 0.3 and 0.4 vs. 0.4 cases do not differ substantially from the hyperprior. Even where the response rates are identical between datasets, the posterior means remain close to the prior mean of 0.667 at values of 0.698 and 0.692 for external data samples sizes of 100 and 200, respectively.

We can see from Table 1 that where the response rates differ substantially (0.4 vs. 0.2) between the current and external data, the NPP's ability to down-weight the external data prevents the posterior mean response rates from being pulled aggressively towards the pooled response rate of 0.267. For example, with sample response rates of 0.4 and 0.2 and sample sizes of 100 and 200 for the current and external data, respectively, the response rates are 0.378, 0.364, and 0.333 under the Beta(0.5, 0.5), Beta(1, 1), and Beta(2, 1), respectively. Nonetheless the choice of hyperprior still impacts where these point estimates fall on the interval [0.267, 0.400] between the two extremes of complete pooling and no

Figure 2: Discount Parameter Posteriors vs. Beta(1, 1) Hyperprior (grey)

borrowing from the external data.

Unsurprisingly, the amount of borrowing also has a significant impact on the precision of the response rate estimates. For example, with sample sizes of 100 and 200 for the current and external data, respectively, and a Beta(0.5, 0.5) hyperprior, the width of the 95% CrI for the response rate decreases from 0.205 to 0.136 when the external data response rates rises from 0.2 to match the current data response rate of 0.4. When instead using a Beta(2, 1) hyperprior, the width of the 95% CrI instead falls from 0.194 to 0.127. If we were able to induce even more borrowing when response rates are identical we would expect further reductions in the width of the 95% CrIs¹, however, achieving this would potentially require hyperpriors that favour even more aggressive information borrowing.

4 Discussion

The findings of this study suggest that when there are large discrepancies in sample response rates between current study data and available external data from which to borrow, dynamic borrowing via a normalized power prior (NPP) tends to materially down-weight the external data—i.e. the NPP tends to reduce borrowing from the external data when outcomes are inconsistent between data sources. This down-weighting becomes even more pronounced when the external data source has a larger sample size—i.e. more evidence of a

¹For reference, the width of a frequentist 95% confidence interval would be 0.111 under the full pooling scenario with response rates of 0.4 in both samples and a total sample size of 300.

Figure 3: Discount Parameter Posteriors vs. Beta(2, 1) Hyperprior (grey)

material discrepancy in outcomes between data sources results in reduced borrowing from the external data.

The ability of the NPP to down-weight external data when outcomes materially differ tempers the degree to which response estimates are pulled towards the pooled estimate. This may be a desirable property for mitigating the risk of bias (and potentially elevated type-I error) when designing a study which incorporates external data (see Viele et al.[1] for additional discussion and demonstration of type-I error impacts under dynamic borrowing). Nonetheless, any borrowing from an external data source has the potential to introduce bias and careful consideration of potential type-I and type-II error operating characteristics should be undertaken during the design stage[3, 4, 5].

However, when outcomes are highly consistent between data sources, the NPP doesn't tend to strongly favour substantial borrowing. In fact, where outcomes are consistent between data sources, the posterior distributions for the discount parameter do not tend to differ much from the chosen hyperprior—i.e. if the hyperprior doesn't favour a high degree of borrowing ex ante, the NPP is likely to induce at best a modest amount of borrowing from the external data even when outcomes are highly consistent. This may limit the potential for the NPP to improve precision (and potentially reduce type-II error).

These results suggest that the NPP provides a dynamic borrowing approach which is capable of down-weighting the external data when it is inconsistent with the current data but which doesn't tend to as strongly favour a large amount of borrowing when the data sources are consistent. Furthermore, we can see that where response rates are similar between data sources the choice of hyperprior has a major impact on the amount of borrowing and

does not induce a high degree of borrowing unless favoured by the choice of hyperprior. Nonetheless, our results suggest that the NPP is still a practical tool for inducing dynamic borrowing from external data sources for the design of trials in rare disease indications in order to improve power/precision where it is difficult to recruit patients. The key takeaway of this study is that careful attention should be given to hyperprior choice when designing and evaluating the operating characteristics of a study using normalized power priors.

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A.1 MCMC Trace Plots

Thinning of 200 was applied to all MCMC trace plots to improve readability in light of the large number of MCMC iterations. All trace plots for the NPP discount parameter (α_0) and response rate parameter (θ) exhibit good mixing under all scenarios considered. Additionally, \hat{R} statistics for these two parameters are less than 1.001 for each scenario. These results are strongly indicative that MCMC convergence was achieved.

Parameter: alpha0
Hyperprior: Beta(1, 1)

Parameter: alpha0
Hyperprior: Beta(2, 1)

Parameter: theta
Hyperprior: Beta(0.5, 0.5)

Parameter: theta
Hyperprior: Beta(1, 1)

A.2 Simulation Code

```

rm(list = ls())
library(rstan)
library(gridExtra)
library(ggplot2)
library(viridis)
setwd("~/../Repos/RD2023001_NPP_Priors/results")
set.seed(01102023)

#Set MCMC parameters
MCMC_ITERS <- 100000
MCMC_BURNIN <- 10000
MCMC_CHAINS <- 4
MCMC_THIN <- 1

#Stan code
stan_code <- "
functions {
  real beta_with_const_lpdf(real x, real alpha, real beta) {
    return -lbeta(alpha, beta) + (alpha - 1) * log(x) + (beta - 1) * log(1 - x);
  }
}
data {
  int<lower=1> y0;
  int<lower=1> n0;
  int<lower=1> y;
  int<lower=1> n;

  real<lower=0> a;
  real<lower=0> b;
  real<lower=0> c;

```

```

    real<lower=0> d;
  }
  parameters {
    real<lower=0,upper=1> alpha0;
    real<lower=0,upper=1> theta;
  }
  model {
    y ~ binomial(n, theta);
    theta ~ beta_with_const(alpha0 * y0 + a, alpha0 * (n0 - y0) + b);
    alpha0 ~ beta_with_const(c, d);
  }
"

#Compile Stan code
mdl <- stan_model(model_code = stan_code)

#Create object to hold tabular results and specify simulation scenarios
results <- expand.grid(n = c(100), n0 = c(100, 200), p = c(0.4),
  p0 = c(0.2, 0.3, 0.4))
results <- rbind(cbind(results, c = rep(0.5, nrow(results)),
  d = rep(0.5, nrow(results))),
  cbind(results, c = rep(1, nrow(results)),
  d = rep(1, nrow(results))),
  cbind(results, c = rep(2, nrow(results)),
  d = rep(1, nrow(results))))
results$y <- round(results$n * results$p, 0)
results$p <- results$y / results$n
results$y0 <- round(results$n0 * results$p0, 0)
results$p0 <- results$y0 / results$n0
results <- results[,c("c", "d", "n", "y", "p", "n0", "y0", "p0")]
results$alpha0 <- ""
results$theta <- ""
results$alpha0_IQR <- ""

#Function to extract 95% credible intervals (CrI)
CrI <- function(fit, param, digits = 3) {
  r <- as.character(sprintf(paste0("%.", digits, "f"),
    c(round(summary(fit)$summary[param,"mean"], digits),
    round(summary(fit)$summary[param,"2.5%"], digits),
    round(summary(fit)$summary[param,"97.5%"],
    digits))))
  return(paste0(r[1], " [", r[2], ", ", r[3], "]")
)

#Run MCMC for each scenario and store results
fit <- list()
for (i in 1:nrow(results)) {
  fit[[i]] <- sampling(mdl, data = list(n = results$n[i], y = results$y[i],
    n0 = results$n0[i], y0 = results$y0[i],
    a = 1, b = 1,
    c = results$c[i], d = results$d[i]),
    iter = MCMC_ITERS, warmup = MCMC_BURNIN,
    chains = MCMC_CHAINS, thin = MCMC_THIN)
  results$alpha0[i] <- CrI(fit[[i]], "alpha0", digits = 3)
  results$theta[i] <- CrI(fit[[i]], "theta", digits = 3)
}

#Print results table
results$hyperprior <- paste0("Beta(", results$c, ", ", results$d, ")")
results$n_n0 <- paste0(results$n, " : ", results$n0)
tbl <- results[,c("hyperprior", "p", "p0", "n_n0", "theta", "alpha0")]
knitr::kable(tbl, caption = paste0("Results under Various Scenarios (Posterior",
  "Means and 95% CrIs Reported Except where",
  "Otherwise Noted)")

#Output results table formatted for LaTeX
cat(paste0("\hline\n", "\\textbf{Hyperprior} & \\textbf{$p$} & \\textbf{$p_0$}",
  "& \\textbf{$n:n_0$} & \\textbf{Response Rate ($\\theta$)} &",

```

```

      "\\textbf{Discount Parameter ( $\alpha_0$ )}\\\\"\\n", "\\hline\\n")
for (h in unique(tbl$hyperprior)) {
  cat(paste(apply(tbl[tbl$hyperprior == h,], 1,
    function(x) {paste0(paste0(x, collapse = " & "), "\\\\"\\n)}),
    sep = "\\n"))
  cat("\\hline\\n")
}

#Produce figures
for (h in unique(results$hyperprior)) {
  gdat <- NULL
  for (i in which(results$hyperprior == h)) {
    tmp <- data.frame(x = c(rstan::extract(fit[[i]])["alpha0"]))
    tmp$Size <- paste0("(", results$n[i], ", ", results$n0[i], ")")
    tmp$Response <- paste0("(", results$p[i], ", ", results$p0[i], ")")

    if (!is.null(gdat)) {
      gdat <- rbind(gdat, tmp)
    } else {
      gdat <- tmp
    }
  }
  fig <-
  ggplot(gdat) +
  theme_bw(base_size = 16) + theme(legend.position = "right") +
  geom_density(mapping = aes(x = x, color = Response, linetype = Size),
    linewidth = 1.0) +
  geom_function(fun = function(x) {dbeta(x, shape1 = results$c[i],
    shape2 = results$d[i])},
    color = "darkgrey", linewidth = 1.0,
    xlim = c(0.0006, 0.9994)) +
  xlab(bquote("Discount Parameter" ~ group("(", alpha[0], ")"))) +
  ylab("Density") +
  scale_color_discrete(name = bquote("Response," ~
    group("(", list(p, p[0]), ")")
    == ~ "")) +
  scale_linetype_discrete(name = bquote("Size," ~
    group("(", list(n, n[0]), ")")
    == ~ "")) +
  ggtitle(paste0("Hyperprior: Beta(", results$c[i], ", ", results$d[i], ")"))

  print(fig)
  postscript(paste0("fig_", gsub("[, ]", "_", gsub("\\.", "_", h)), ".eps"))
  print(fig)
  dev.off()
}

#Output summaries
for (i in 1:length(fit)) {
  cat(paste0("Scenario ", i, ":\n\n"))
  print(fit[[i]], digits_summary = 3)
  cat("\n\n")
}

#Implement trace plot function that allows for thinning
trplt <- function(fit, par, thin = 1, main = "") {
  gdat <- NULL
  nchain <- length(fit@sim$samples)
  for (i in 1:nchain) {
    index <- (floor(fit@stan_args[[i]]$warmup / fit@stan_args[[i]]$thin) + 1):
      floor(fit@stan_args[[i]]$iter / fit@stan_args[[i]]$thin)
    tmp <- data.frame(y = fit@sim$samples[[i]][[par]][index],
      x = index)

    tmp$Chain <- i
    tmp <- tmp[seq(1, nrow(tmp), thin),]
    if (is.null(gdat))
      gdat <- tmp
    else

```

```

      gdat <- rbind(gdat, tmp)
    }
    gdat$Chain <- as.factor(gdat$Chain)
    plt <- ggplot(gdat, aes(x = x, y = y, color = Chain)) +
      geom_line() + xlab("Iteration") + ylab(par) +
      scale_color_manual(values = inferno(nchain + 2)[c(-1, -(nchain+2))]) +
      ylim(0, 1) + ggtitle(main)
    return(plt)
  }

#produce trace plots for all scenarios
j <- 1
for (v in c("alpha0", "theta")) {
  k <- 1
  plt <- list()
  for (i in 1:nrow(results)) {
    plt[[k]] <-
      trplt(fit[[i]], v, thin = 200,
            main = bquote(group("(", list(n, n[0]), ")") ==
                          group("(", list(. (results$n[i]), . (results$n0[i])), ")") ~
                          "and" ~
                          group("(", list(p, p[0]), ")") ==
                          group("(", list(. (results$p[i]), . (results$p0[i])), ")")))
    k <- k + 1
    if (i == nrow(results) || results$hyperprior[i] !=
        results$hyperprior[i+1]) {
      postscript(paste0("traceplots_", j, ".eps"))
      grid.arrange(grobs = plt,
                  top = paste0("Parameter: ", v,
                              "\nHyperprior: ", results$hyperprior[i]),
                  ncol = 2)
      dev.off()
      plt <- list()
      k <- 1
      j <- j + 1
    }
  }
}

```